

Notes

Spectrophotometric Studies on Fe (ii)-2 Hydroxy-5 Methyl Acetophenone-Ethylenediamineanil Complex. Part I

G. B. JOSHI

University Department of Chemistry, Saurashtra University
Bhavnagar

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THE 2-Hydroxy-5-methyl-acetophenone-ethylenediamine-anil has been reported to be a chelating agent for few metal ions¹. However, the spectrophotometric studies of its metal chelates have not been done systematically so far. The present work deals with the determination of composition and stability constant of Fe(ii) chelate with HMAEA reagent by Job's method of continuous variation^{2,3}, mole ratio method⁴ and slope ratio method⁵.

Experimental

Preparation of 2-Hydroxy-5-methyl-acetophenone-ethylene-diamine-anil¹.

2-Hydroxy-5-methyl-acetophenone was prepared by Fries reaction of p-cresyl-acetate⁶. 2-Hydroxy-5-methyl-acetophenone (2.0 mole) and ethylene diamine (1.0 mole) in absolute alcohol were refluxed for one hour, when a yellow anil was obtained. It was recrystallised from alcohol m.p. 201°.

Reaction with Fe²⁺ ions: A stock solution of ferrous sulphate ($1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$) was prepared in double distilled water and standardised by the general method. One percent ethanolic solution of the reagent was used. It gave reddish brown chelate with Fe²⁺ at pH 2.5-3.0.

Effect of pH: Preliminary experiments showed that the colour of the complex between pH 2.5 to 4.0 is reddish brown. At pH lower than 2.5, there is no coloration and above the pH 4, the complex was unstable. The study was therefore confined to the pH range 2.5 to 3.0 where maximum colour intensity was obtained. This pH range was obtained using sodium acetate-acetic acid buffer and the pH was measured by using the pH meter (Systronic) with glass electrode (0-13 pH) and a saturated calomel electrode.

Effect of Varying Solvent Composition: The complex remains soluble in ethanol water mixture (70:30) and the solution becomes turbid on further dilution with water. No change in colour has been observed on changing the composition of the solvent and the ethanolic solution of the complex remains stable for 24 hr.

Spectrophotometric Study:

Absorption Measurements: The absorbance measurements were carried out at 500 nm using "Spectronic 20".

An equimolar solutions of ferrous sulphate ($1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$) and reagent solution in ethanol ($1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$) in the ratio of 2:1, 1:1, 1:2 and 1:3 at pH 2.5-3.0 were mixed and the final volume was made 10 ml by adding required amount of water and alcohol to keep alcohol water composition same in all cases. The absorption spectra of all solutions were recorded. In all cases the maximum absorption was found to be at 500 nm and 438 nm suggest that reagent forms only one type of complex with Fe²⁺ ion. The Beer's Law has been varified at 500 nm and 438 nm at pH 2.5-3.0.

Composition and Stability Constant of the Complex: Using Job's method^{2,3} molar ratio method⁴ and slope ratio method⁵, the stoichiometry of the Fe-HMAEA complex has been found to be 1:1. The stability constant calculated from these methods was 1.34×10^6 . The molar absorptivity of the complex is found to be $1:1 \times 10^3$.

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New Synthesis of 6-Nitro-4-Hydroxy and 8-Nitro-4-Hydroxy Cinnolines

P. S. FERNANDES, V. V. NADKARNY. (MISS) G.A. JABBAR and (MISS) R.P. JANI

Nadkarny-Sacasa Research Laboratory, St. Xavier's College, Bombay-1.

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CINNOLINE, a heterocyclic binuclear base containing two vicinal nitrogen atoms was first synthesized by Richter¹ by cyclisation of an aryldiazonium compound containing an unsaturated group at the ortho-position. 4-Hydroxy cinnolines were synthesized from 2-nitrophenylpropionic acid as well as 2-amino-phenylpropionic acid² and 2-aminophenylacetylenes³. Further, cinnolines not containing any hydroxy group at the 4-position was synthesized by a number of workers, by cyclising the diazotised o-aminophenyl-